

Rhino Conservation Monitoring System (Animal Detection Using Background Color Filter)

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Abstract— As we know, there are a lot of different types of animal exist in the forest. Some of them are rare animals that are protected by government. Technology can help people discover the condition of animal that is protected by the government. With the forest characteristic which is the scenery dominated with green color, the filter color can be used for animal detection purposed. Image processing can be used by the system to separate the animal picture and the non-animal picture. Picture will be convert into 2 colors, black and white. The scenery color, which is dominated with green pixels and black pixels, will be converted into white pixels and other color pixels will be converted into black pixels. From the proportion of white pixel and black pixel, we can assume the image category, the animal picture or the non-animal picture. Animal detection program is implemented on Raspberry Pi. From the test, system can separate the animal picture and the non-animal picture with the green forest scenery. The system can separate the pictures as long as the percentage of black pixel is above 10%. The system will always process for every new picture on the system and separate it automatically.

Keywords: Image Processing; Animal Detection; Color Filter; Raspberry Pi;

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, technology development is already used in many segments to help people get their need easier. One of the technology's development, image processing, has For example, the government can make use of technology to help them monitor and protect rare animal. The rhino conservation monitoring system can be used to help government on rare animals concern.

The camera's system will take picture or record video everytime sensors sense an object. If the camera record a video, the video will send to video's folder directly on the

Raspberry Pi, but if the camera take a picture, the system will process it after it send to image's folder on Raspberry Pi. The image processing on Raspberry Pi is functioned as animal detection. This is to make sure what the sensor sense is really an animal. After the system process the image, the pictures will be separated into 2 types image files, the non-animal pictures and the animal pictures. The animal pictures and the video files, will be sent to another Raspberry Pi which is installed on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) with DTN architecture. After the UAV get some files, in data center, the files from UAV will be processed again to separate image files into specific classification. This separation process to help user separate

the rhino pictures and not. System's block diagram is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Block Diagram

The first image processing stage on the system is to separate the animal pictures with the non-animal pictures. Image processing is a process using mathematical operations that the input is an image file. The result of the image processing is not always an image, but it can be a parameter or characteristics that related to the image input. For animal detection, there are several processes known as image pre-processing.

A. Gaussian Blur

Gaussian Blur is a technique of blurring image based on Gaussian Function. This process is to make the picture smoother by reduce the image noise and detail. Gaussian Blur use Gaussian Function to calculate the transformation, to apply for each pixel in the image. For 1 dimension, the equation is given by (1)

$$G(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

For the 2 dimensions, the equation is given by (2)

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (2)$$

From the equation, the distance in horizontal axis from the origin is symbolized by x , for the vertical axis is symbolized by y and for the standard deviation is symbolized by σ .

B. Converting RGB to HSV

Normally, The RGB color space is used to tell the color of an object^[1]. The difference between RGB and HSV color space is how they describe the color's term. RGB color space describes color's term by amount of primary colors that are red, green and blue. HSV color space describes colors in terms of the hue, saturation and value. The HSV color space describes color similarly with human eyes when they tends to perceive color. The HSV color space, unlike RGB color space, separates image intensity from the color information. HSV color space has better visualization^[2]. Some devices only support HSV color space.

II. RELATED WORK

The background color filter is used to implement animal detection process into Rhino conservation monitoring system. The BGR color from the image will be converted into HSV colorspace as image pre-processing.

Previously, HSV model is used to detect food on plate. HSV model is very efficient for identifying the object based on hue and value. HSV model separate the plate from the background and separate the food with the plate. The food can be identified by hue of the food^[3].

On the previous work, image processing is used for detecting and counting pothole on the image. It used a gaussian-filtering and clustering based on image segmentation as image pre-processing. For processing the image, it used several method to make a conclusion. For the fasting computation, K-Means clustering based segmentation is feasible. Meanwhile, edge detection is preferable for specificity^[4].

On the previous implementation, image processing techniques is used for recognizing matured cinnamon tree. The Speed Up Robust Features is used as image pre-processing to gain some informations from leaves and used Support Vector Machine to predict the maturity level of cinnamon tree^[5].

III. DESIGN

The animal detection on Raspberry Pi is using python language program. System will identify the file's type. If the file's type is a video file, system will move the file into folder that is prepared for video files. If the file's type is an image, the system will pre-process and after that process the image file to know the image is an animal image or non-animal image. If it is an animal image, system will move it into a folder that is prepared for animal image files, but if it is non-animal image, system will move the file into a folder that is prepared for non-animal image files. The flow chart of program is shown in Figure 2.

For image files, there are 2 image pre-processing method that are used., Gaussian-Blur method and converting RGB to HSV color space. Gaussian-Blur is used to make image smoother by reduce the image noise and detail. After the image become smoother, the image color space is converted into HSV from RGB colorspace. The next step is program will mask all green and black colors on the image in other words the green and black pixel will be converted into white pixel. The other colors that are not masked, will be converted into black pixel. The system will calculate the percentage of black pixel compared with all pixel that the image has. If the black pixel's percentage is above 10%, system will assume there are an object (animal) on the picture. If the percentage below 10%, system will assume there are no object on the picture.

Figure 2 Flow Chart

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The animal detection program work well on Raspberry Pi. The program can separate video files, non-animal image files and animal image files. System can separate the non-animal image files and animal image files as long as the background pictures are forest and leaf which is dominated with green and black color. The result of masking process for animal picture is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Animal Picture Masking

The result of masking process for non-animal picture is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 Non-animal Picture Masking

From the Figure 3 and Figure 4, system can convert green and black color into white pixel. For the result from the test using same background image can be seen in Figure 5. The image has same background but the difference is one picture without an object and the other one the picture with an object. The background from those images nearly completely converted into white pixel. It means background color from the images are dominated with green and black colors. The system converted those image successfully.

Figure 5 Object and Non-object Picture Masking

The next test is to know if whole program works perfectly. The test is using several random files, images and videos, if the file is an image file, system will write the black pixel percentage with explanation about the image. The result of whole program test can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Result of Whole Program Test

No	File's Name	Percentage	Files Type	Fit with the Fact
1	015 - Ada.jpg	15,91%	Animal Image	Yes
2	07 - Ada.jpg	25,33%	Animal Image	Yes
3	0717 - Ada.jpg	36,25%	Animal Image	Yes
4	08 - Ada.jpg	15,66%	Animal Image	Yes
5	10 - tidak.jpg	1,15%	Non-animal Image	Yes
6	103 - Ada.jpg	21,42%	Animal Image	Yes
7	11 - tidak.jpg	4,15%	Non-animal Image	Yes
8	163 - tidak.jpg	6,82%	Non-animal Image	Yes
9	12 - tidak.jpg	1,39%	Non-animal Image	Yes
10	01.mp4	-	Video	Yes
11	02.mp4	-	Video	Yes
12	17 - tidak.jpg	4,14%	Non-animal Image	Yes

Final test is to know if the program will automatically process every new file in the source directory. The result is program process the new file successfully. The test use 3 types of file, video file, non-animal image file and animal image file. The files move to their own folder that system has made.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on several tests, the program can separate the files depend on the file's type. System can detect an object in an image with forest (green and black color) background. The program has been implemented on the Raspberry Pi and work perfectly. The Percentage of non-animal image files with forest and leaf as background are below 10%. As long as the image file have percentage above 10%, the system will assume it as animal image file.

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